

parasitized YSB egg masses were collected in an unsprayed area of the University research farm. In the laboratory, 3 egg masses of uniform size, each attached in situ to a rice leaf, were kept on filter paper in a 7.5 cm-diam petri dish and exposed to the insecticide solution under a Potter's spray tower. After drying, the egg masses were incubated in rearing tubes at 29°C and 55% relative humidity. Each set of three was replicated thrice and an unsprayed set of three egg masses was kept for comparison. Emerged parasites, borer larvae, and unemerged larvae were counted after the unemerged larvae were softened in diluted potassium hydroxide.

Treated egg masses yielded a high percentage of parasites and host larvae in all test concentrations. In general, host larva and parasite emergence was significantly lower in the treated set than in the untreated (see table). The varying rate of parasite emergence in the insecticide treatments and the untreated set was caused by the difference in field parasitization rate rather than by the insecticides. Insecticide action on developing parasites

Percent emergence of larvae and parasite adults from insecticide-treated and untreated host eggs at Bhubaneswar, India, Feb 1982.

Insecticide	Concentration (ai %)	Emergence (%)			
		Larvae		Adults	
		Eggs (treated)	Eggs (untreated)	Eggs (treated)	Eggs (untreated)
Chlorpyrifos	0.025	32.7	50.0	10.3	32.6
	0.050	56.0	57.1	6.0	12.2
	0.075	22.2	85.7	50.0	46.8
Fenitrothion	0.025	24.5	2.4	11.6	20.0
	0.050	43.8	48.5	30.1	81.3
	0.075	33.5	35.7	41.1	60.0
Fenthion	0.025	22.6	59.1	45.4	12.0
	0.050	67.6	76.9	70.9	65.0
	0.075	49.8	59.0	66.7	82.4
Formothion	0.025	43.6	78.6	60.2	63.6
	0.050	24.4	52.8	36.0	20.0
	0.075	22.3	74.1	51.5	54.7
Phenthoate	0.025	77.5	53.6	47.1	66.7
	0.050	28.0	26.8	26.0	30.0
	0.075	33.1	91.0	73.4	66.7
Phosphamidon	0.025	16.4	11.1	17.2	28.6
	0.050	49.5	60.0	63.6	12.0
	0.075	53.6	43.3	43.5	60.0
Quinalphos	0.025	19.2	39.3	25.0	77.5
	0.050	32.7	44.8	41.3	38.5
	0.075	82.1	97.7	47.6	58.5
LSD 5%	Insecticide		2.6		2.3
	Untreated vs treated		0.8		0.7
	Interaction		3.6		3.2

and host eggs was adequately circumvented by the hairy matrix surrounding

the egg mass. The chorion of the egg may also have limited insecticide penetration. □

Insect pests of rice in the Sikkim Hills

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Surveys from 1977 to 1981 in hilly rice growing areas in Sikkim identified many insect species (see table). Few insects had pest status. Stem borers *Chilo suppressalis* (Walk.), *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walk.), and *Sesamia inferens* (Walk.) were the major pests. They cause 7.2% deadhearts at tillering and 19.5% whiteheads after flowering. Leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guen.) was a serious pest in Jul 1979, with 22.3 larvae/m² in Ranipul. Usually it is of minor importance. Brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* (Horv.) were generally minor pests, but in 1978 WBPH infestation was high. Gall midge, caseworm, grasshopper, rice bugs, rice hispa, rice leafhoppers, semilooper, spittle bug, leaf beetles, and rice skipper were of minor importance. □

Rice insects in the Sikkim hills.

Common name	Scientific name	Family	Order	% infestation
Striped stem borer	<i>Chilo suppressalis</i> (Walk.)	Pyalidae	Lepidoptera	7.2 to 19.5
Tussock caterpillar	<i>Euproctis varians</i> (Walk.)	Lymantiridae	Lepidoptera	—
Pink stem borer	<i>Sesamia inferens</i> (Walk.)	Noctuidae	Lepidoptera	7.2 to 19.5
Rice swarming caterpillar	<i>Spodoptera mauritia</i> (Boisd.)	Noctuidae	Lepidoptera	—
Common cutworm	<i>S. litura</i> (F.)	Noctuidae	Lepidoptera	—
Ear-cutting caterpillar	<i>Mythimna separata</i> (Walk.)	Noctuidae	Lepidoptera	—
Semilooper	<i>Mocis</i> [=Remigia] <i>frugalis</i> (Fabr.)	Noctuidae	Lepidoptera	—
Rice skipper	<i>Parnara guttata</i> Bremer & Grey	Hesperiidae	Lepidoptera	—
Yellow stem borer	<i>Scirpophaga</i> [=Tryporyza] <i>incertulas</i> (Walk.)	Pyalidae	Lepidoptera	7.2 to 19.5
Leaf folder	<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i> (Guen.)	Pyalidae	Lepidoptera	—
Rice caseworm	<i>Nymphula depunctalis</i> (Guen.)	Pyalidae	Lepidoptera	—
Rice bug	<i>Leptocorisa</i> sp.	Alydidae	Hemiptera	12 to 15
Stink bug	<i>Cletus</i> sp.	Coreidae	Hemiptera	—
Spittle bug	<i>Cosmoscarta</i> sp.	Cercopidae	Hemiptera	—
Brown planthopper	<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i> (Stål)	Delphacidae	Hemiptera	—
Whitebacked planthopper	<i>Sogatella furcifera</i> (Horv.)	Delphacidae	Hemiptera	—
Leaf rolling weevils	<i>Centrocorynus scutellaris</i> (Gyll)	Attellabidae	Coleoptera	—
	<i>C. rufulus</i> Voss.	Attellabidae	Coleoptera	—
Root weevil	<i>Phytoscaphus triangularis</i> (Oliv.)	Curculionidae	Coleoptera	—
Rice gall midge	<i>Orseolia oryzae</i> (Wood-Mason)	Cecidomyiidae	Diptera	—
Green leafhopper	<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i> (Stål)	Cicadellidae	Homoptera	—
Zigzag leafhopper	<i>Recilia dorsalis</i> (Motsch.)	Cicadellidae	Homoptera	—
Aphid	<i>Rhopalosiphum padi</i> (Linnaeus)	Aphididae	Homoptera	—
Small grasshopper	<i>Oxya chinensis</i> (Thunberg)	Acrididae	Orthopter	5 to 8